

On Involute and Evolute Curves of Spacelike Curve with a Spacelike Principal Normal in Minkowski 3-Space

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Abstract In this study, we have generalized the involute and evolute curves of the spacelike curve α with a spacelike principal normal in Minkowski 3-Space. Firstly, we have shown that, the length between the spacelike curves α and β is constant. Furthermore, the Frenet frame of the involute curve β has been found as depend on curvatures of the curve α . We have determined the curve α is planar in which conditions. Secondly, we have found transformation matrix between the evolute curve β and the curve α . Finally, we have computed the curvatures of the evolute curve β .

Key Words: Spacelike curve, involutes, evolutes, Minkowski 3-space.

AMS(2000): 53A04,53B30,53A35.

§1. Preliminaries

Let $R^3 = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3) | x_1, x_2, x_3 \in R\}$ be a 3-dimensional vector space, and let $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ and $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3)$ be two vectors in IR^3 . The Lorentz scalar product of x and y is defined by

$$\langle x, y \rangle_L = -x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3,$$

$E_1^3 = (R^3, \langle x, y \rangle_L)$ is called 3-dimensional Lorentzian space, Minkowski 3-Space or 3-dimensional semi-euclidean space. The vector x in IE_1^3 is called a spacelike vector, null vector or a timelike vector if $\langle x, x \rangle_L > 0$ or $x = 0$, $\langle x, x \rangle_L = 0$ or $\langle x, x \rangle_L < 0$, respectively. For $x \in E_1^3$, the norm of the vector x defined by $\|x\|_L = \sqrt{|\langle x, x \rangle_L|}$, and x is called a unit vector if $\|x\|_L = 1$. For any $x, y \in E_1^3$, Lorentzian vectoral product of x and y is defined by

$$x \wedge_L y = (x_3y_2 - x_2y_3, x_3y_1 - x_1y_3, x_1y_2 - x_2y_1).$$

We denote by $\{T(s), N(s), B(s)\}$ the moving Frenet frame along the curve $\alpha(s)$. Then $T(s), N(s)$ and $B(s)$ are tangent, the principal normal and the binormal vector of the curve

¹Received November 24, 2008. Accepted January 12, 2009.

$\alpha(s)$, respectively. Depending on the causal character of the curve α , we have the following Frenet-Serret formulae:

If α is a spacelike curve with a spacelike principal normal N ,

$$T' = \kappa N, \quad N = -\kappa T + \tau B, \quad B' = \tau N \quad (1.1)$$

$$\langle T, T \rangle_L = \langle N, N \rangle_L = 1, \langle B, B \rangle_L = -1, \langle T, N \rangle_L = \langle N, B \rangle_L = \langle T, B \rangle_L = 0.$$

If α is a spacelike curve with a timelike principal normal N ,

$$T' = \kappa N, \quad N = \kappa T + \tau B, \quad B' = \tau N \quad (1.2)$$

$$\langle T, T \rangle_L = \langle B, B \rangle_L = 1, \langle N, N \rangle_L = -1, \langle T, N \rangle_L = \langle N, B \rangle_L = \langle T, B \rangle_L = 0.$$

If α is a timelike curve and finally,

$$T' = \kappa N, \quad N = \kappa T + \tau B, \quad B' = -\tau N \quad (1.3)$$

$$\langle T, T \rangle_L = -1, \langle B, B \rangle_L = \langle N, N \rangle_L = 1, \langle T, N \rangle_L = \langle N, B \rangle_L = \langle T, B \rangle_L = 0.$$

known in [2]. If the curve α is non-unit speed, then

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{\|\alpha'(t) \wedge_L \alpha''(t)\|_L}{\|\alpha'(t)\|_L^3}, \quad \tau(t) = \frac{\det(\alpha'(t), \alpha''(t), \alpha'''(t))}{\|\alpha'(t) \wedge_L \alpha''(t)\|_L^2}. \quad (1.4)$$

If the curve α is unit speed, then

$$\kappa(s) = \|\alpha''(s)\|_L, \quad \tau(s) = \|B'(s)\|_L. \quad (1.5)$$

§2. The involute of spacelike curve with a spacelike principal normal

Definition 2.1 *Let unit speed spacelike curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow E_1^3$ with a principal normal and spacelike curve $\beta : I \rightarrow E_1^3$ with a spacelike principal normal be given. For $\forall s \in I$, then the curve β is called the involute of the curve α , if the tangent at the point $\alpha(s)$ to the curve α passes through the tangent at the point $\beta(s)$ to the curve β and*

$$\langle T^*(s), T(s) \rangle_L = 0. \quad (2.1)$$

Let the Frenet-Serret frames of the curves α and β be $\{T, N, B\}$ and $\{T^, N^*, B^*\}$, respectively. In this case, the causal characteristics of the Frenet-Serret frames of the curves α and β must be of the form.*

$$\{T \text{ spacelike}, N \text{ spacelike}, B \text{ timelike}\}$$

and

$$\{T^* \text{ spacelike}, N^* \text{ spacelike}, B^* \text{ timelike}\}.$$

Theorem 2.1 *Let the curve β be involute of the the curve α and let k be a constant real number. Then*

$$\beta(s) = \alpha(s) + (k - s)T(s). \quad (2.2)$$

Proof The curve $\beta(s)$ may be given as

$$\beta(s) = \alpha(s) + u(s)T(s) \quad (2.3)$$

If we take the derivative Eq. (2.3), then we have

$$\beta'(s) = (1 + u'(s))T(s) + u(s)\kappa(s)N(s).$$

Since the curve β is involute of the curve α , $\langle T^*(s), T(s) \rangle_L = 0$. Then, we get

$$1 + u'(s) = 0 \text{ or } u(s) = k - s. \quad (2.4)$$

Thus we get

$$\beta(s) - \alpha(s) = (k - s)T(s) \quad (2.5)$$

□

Corollary 2.2 *The distance between the curves β and α is $|k - s|$.*

Proof If we take the norm in Eq. (2.5), then we get

$$\|\beta(s) - \alpha(s)\|_L = |k - s|. \quad (2.6)$$

□

Theorem 2.3 *Let the curve β be involute of the the curve α , then*

$$\begin{bmatrix} T^* \\ N^* \\ B^* \end{bmatrix} = (|\kappa^2 - \tau^2|)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \kappa & 0 & -\tau \\ -\tau & 0 & \kappa \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix}$$

Proof If we take the derivative Eq. (2.5), we can write

$$\beta'(s) = (k - s)\kappa(s)N(s)$$

and

$$\|\beta'(s)\|_L = |(k - s)\kappa(s)|.$$

Furthermore, we get

$$T^*(s) = \frac{\beta'(s)}{\|\beta'(s)\|_L} = \frac{(k - s)\kappa(s)}{|(k - s)\kappa(s)|}N(s).$$

From the last equation, we must have

$$T^*(s) = N(s) \text{ or } T^*(s) = -N(s).$$

We assume that $T^*(s) = N(s)$. Let's denote the coordinate function on IR by x . Then, for $\forall s \in IR$, $x(s) = s$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\beta'(s) &= (k-s)\kappa(s)N(s), \\ \beta' &= (k-x)\kappa N.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\beta'' &= -\kappa N + (k-x)\kappa' N + (k-x)\kappa(-\kappa T + \tau B) \\ \beta'' &= -(k-x)\kappa^2 T + [(k-x)\kappa' - \kappa] N + (k-x)\kappa \tau B\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have

$$\beta' \wedge_L \beta'' = (k-x)^2 \kappa^2 (-\tau T + \kappa B)$$

and

$$\left\| \beta' \wedge_L \beta'' \right\|_L = |k-x|^2 \kappa^2 \sqrt{|\tau^2 - \kappa^2|}.$$

Furthermore, we get

$$B^* = \frac{\beta' \wedge_L \beta''}{\left\| \beta' \wedge_L \beta'' \right\|} = \frac{(k-x)^2 \kappa^2 (-\tau T + \kappa B)}{(k-x)^2 \kappa^2 \sqrt{|\tau^2 - \kappa^2|}} = \frac{-\tau T + \kappa B}{\sqrt{|\kappa^2 - \tau^2|}}.$$

Since $N^* = B^* \wedge_L T^*$, then we obtain

$$N^* = \frac{\tau T - \kappa B}{\sqrt{|\tau^2 - \kappa^2|}}.$$

□

Theorem 2.4 *Let the curve β be involute of the the curve α . Let the curvature and torsion of the curve β be κ^* and τ^* , respectively. Then*

$$\kappa^*(s) = \frac{\sqrt{|(\tau^2 - \kappa^2)(s)|}}{|k-s|\kappa(s)}, \quad \tau^*(s) = \frac{\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s)}{|k-s|\kappa(s)\sqrt{|(\tau^2 - \kappa^2)(s)|}}.$$

Proof From Eq. (1.3) and Eq. (1.4), we have

$$\kappa^*(s) = \frac{|k-s|^2 \kappa^2(s)}{|k-s|^3 \kappa^3(s)} = \frac{\sqrt{|(\tau^2 - \kappa^2)(s)|}}{\kappa(s)|k-s|}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta''' &= \left[\kappa^2 T - (k-x)2\kappa\kappa' T - (k-x)\kappa^2(\kappa N) \right] \\
&+ \left[-\kappa' - \kappa' + (k-x)\kappa'' \right] N \\
&+ \left[-\kappa + (k-x)\kappa' \right] (-\kappa T + \tau B) \\
&+ \left[-\kappa\tau + (k-x)\kappa'\tau + (k-x)\kappa\tau' \right] B \\
&+ \left[(k-x)\kappa\tau \right] (\tau N) \\
&= \left[2\kappa^2 - 3(k-x)\kappa\kappa' \right] T \\
&+ \left[-(k-x)\kappa^3 - 2\kappa' + (k-x)\kappa'' + (k-x)\kappa\tau^2 \right] N \\
&+ \left(-2\kappa\tau + 2(k-x)\kappa'\tau + (k-x)\kappa\tau' \right) B.
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, since

$$\tau^*(s) = \frac{\det(\beta'(s), \beta''(s), \beta'''(s))}{\|\beta'(s) \wedge_L \beta''(s)\|_L^2},$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta &= -(k-x)^2 \kappa^2 \begin{bmatrix} -\kappa & \tau \\ 2\kappa^2 - 3(k-x)\kappa\kappa' & -2\kappa\tau + 2(k-x)\kappa'\tau + (k-x)\kappa\tau' \end{bmatrix} \\
&= -(k-x)^2 \kappa^2 \left[2\kappa^2\tau - 2(k-x)\kappa\kappa'\tau - (k-x)\kappa^2\tau' - 2\kappa^2\tau + 3(k-x)\kappa\kappa'\tau \right] \\
&= (k-x)^3 \kappa^3 (\kappa\tau' - \kappa'\tau) \\
\Delta &= \det(\beta', \beta'', \beta''').
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau^*(s) &= \frac{\kappa^3(k-s)^3 (\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s))}{\kappa^4 |k-s|^4 (\tau^2(s) - \kappa^2(s))}, \\
\tau^*(s) &= \frac{\kappa(s)\tau'(s) - \kappa'(s)\tau(s)}{\kappa(s) |k-x| (\tau^2(s) - \kappa^2(s))}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

From the last equation, we have the following corollaries:

Corollary 2.5 *If the curve α is planar, then its involute curve β is also planar.*

Corollary 2.6 *If the curvature $\kappa \neq 0$ and the torsion $\tau \neq 0$ of the curve α are constant, then the involute curve β is planar, i.e., if the curve α is an ordinary helix, then its involute curve β is planar.*

Corollary 2.7 *If the curvature $\kappa \neq 0$ and the torsion $\tau \neq 0$ of the curve α are not constant but $\frac{\tau}{\kappa}$ is constant, then the involute curve β is planar, i.e. if the curve α is a general helix, then their involute curve β is planar.*

Theorem 2.8 Suppose that the planar curve $\alpha : I \longrightarrow E_1^3$ with arc-length parameter are given. Then, the locus of the center of the curvature of the curve α is the unique involute of the curve α which lies on the plane of the curve α .

Proof The locus of the center of the curvature of the curve α is

$$C(s) = \alpha(s) - \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}N(s), \quad \kappa(s) \neq 0$$

If we take the derivative in the above equation, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC}{ds} &= T - \left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right)' N + \frac{1}{\kappa}(-\kappa T), \\ C' &= -\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right)' N, \\ \langle C', T \rangle_L &= -\left(\frac{1}{\kappa}\right)' \langle N, T \rangle_L, \\ \langle C'(s), T(s) \rangle_L &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the evolute C of the spacelike curve α is the locus of the center of the curvature. Is the curve C planar? If the torsion of the curve C is denoted by τ^* , then

$$\tau^*(s) = \frac{(\kappa' \tau - \kappa \tau')(s)}{\kappa(t) |k - s| \cdot (\tau^2(s) - \kappa^2(s))}.$$

If we take $\tau = 0$, then we have

$$\tau^*(s) = 0$$

Thus, the curve C is planar. □

§3. The evolute of spacelike curve with a spacelike principal normal

Definition 3.1 Let the unit speed spacelike curve α with a spacelike principal normal and the spacelike curve β with the same interval be given. For $\forall s \in I$, the tangent at the point $\beta(s)$ to the curve β passes through the point $\alpha(s)$ and

$$\langle T^*(s), T(s) \rangle_L = 0.$$

Then, β is called the evolute of the curve α . Let the Frenet-Serret frames of the curves α and β be (T, N, B) and (T^*, N^*, B^*) , respectively.

Theorem 3.1 Let the curve β be the evolute of the unit speed spacelike curve α , Then

$$\beta(s) = \alpha(s) + \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}N(s) - \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}[\tanh(\varphi(s) + c)]B(s), \quad (3.1)$$

where $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\varphi(s) + c = \int \tau(s)ds$. Furthermore, in the normal plane of the point $\alpha(s)$ the measure of directed angle between $\beta(s) - \alpha(s)$ and $N(s)$ is

$$\varphi(s) + c.$$

Proof The tangent of the curve β at the point $\beta(s)$ is the line constructed by the vector $T^*(s)$. Since this line passes through the point $\alpha(s)$, the vector $\beta(s) - \alpha(s)$ is perpendicular to the vector $T(s)$. Then

$$\beta(s) - \alpha(s) = \lambda N(s) + \mu B(s). \quad (3.2)$$

If we take the derivative of Eq. (3.2), then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta'(s) &= \alpha'(s) + \lambda' N + \lambda(-\kappa T + \tau B) + \mu' B(s) + \mu(\tau N) \\ \beta'(s) &= (1 - \lambda\kappa)T + (\lambda' + \mu\tau)N + (\lambda\tau + \mu')B. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

According to the definition of the evolute, since $\langle T^*(s), T(s) \rangle = 0$, from Eq. (3.3), we get

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\kappa}, \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$\beta' = (\lambda' + \mu\tau)N + (\lambda\tau + \mu')B. \quad (3.5)$$

From the Eq. (3.2) and Eq. (3.5), the vector field β' is parallel to the vector field $\beta - \alpha$. Then we have

$$\frac{\lambda' + \mu\tau}{\lambda} = \frac{\lambda\tau + \mu'}{\mu}.$$

After that, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \frac{\lambda'\mu - \lambda\mu'}{\lambda^2 - \mu^2} \\ \tau &= -\frac{\left(\frac{\mu}{\lambda}\right)'}{1 - \left(\frac{\mu}{\lambda}\right)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

If we take the integral the last equation, we get

$$\varphi(s) + c = -\arg \tanh \left(\frac{\mu(s)}{\lambda(s)} \right).$$

Hence, we find

$$\mu(s) = -\lambda(s) \tanh(\varphi(s) + c). \quad (3.6)$$

If we substitute Eq. (3.4) and Eq. (3.6) into Eq. (3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(s) &= \alpha(s) + \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}N(s) - \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}[\tanh(\varphi(s) + c)]B(s) \\ \beta(s) &= M(s) - \frac{1}{\kappa(s)}\tanh[\varphi(s) + c]B(s). \end{aligned}$$

Then, we obtain an evolute curve for each $c \in IR$. Since

$$\left\langle \overrightarrow{M(s)\beta(s)}, \overrightarrow{M(s)\alpha(s)} \right\rangle_L = 0,$$

in the Lorentzian triangle which have corners $\beta(s)$, $M(s)$ and $\alpha(s)$, the angle M is right angle in the Lorentzian mean. In the same triangle, the tangent of the angle $\alpha(s)$ is

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\kappa(s)} \tanh[\varphi(s) + c]}{\frac{1}{\kappa(s)}} = \tanh[\varphi(s) + c]. \quad (3.7)$$

Then, the measure of the angle between the vectors $\beta(s) - \alpha(s)$ and $N(s)$ is $\varphi(s) + c$. \square

Theorem 3.2 *Let the spacelike curve $\beta : I \longrightarrow E_1^3$ be evolute of the unit speed spacelike curve $\alpha : I \longrightarrow E_1^3$. If the Frenet-Serret vector fields of the curve β are T^* (spacelike), N^* (space), B^* (timelike), then*

$$\begin{bmatrix} T^* \\ N^* \\ B^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \cosh(\varphi + c) & -\sinh(\varphi + c) \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sinh(\varphi + c) & \cosh(\varphi + c) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

Proof Since the Frenet-Serret vector fields of the curve β are T^* , N^* , B^* and

$$\beta = \alpha + \rho N - \rho \tanh(\varphi + c) B,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \beta'(s) &= \alpha' + \rho' N + \rho(-\kappa T + \tau B) \\ &\quad - \left[\rho' \tanh(\varphi + c) B + \rho \varphi' \operatorname{sech}^2(\varphi + c) B + \rho \tanh(\varphi + c) \tau N \right] \\ &= (1 - \rho\kappa) T + \left(\rho' - \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c) \right) N \\ &\quad + \left[(\rho\tau - \rho\varphi') - \rho' \tanh(\varphi + c) + \rho\varphi' \tanh^2(\varphi + c) \right] B \\ &= \left[\rho' - \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c) \right] N + \left[-\rho' + \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c) \right] B \tanh(\varphi + c) \\ &= \left[\rho' - \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c) \right] [N - \tanh(\varphi + c) B] \\ \beta'(s) &= \left[\frac{\rho' - \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c)}{\cosh(\varphi + c)} \right] [\cosh(\varphi + c) N - \sinh(\varphi + c) B]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

If we take the norm in the Eq. (3.9), then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\beta'(s)\|_L &= \frac{|\rho' - \rho\tau \tanh(\varphi + c)|}{\cosh(\varphi + c)} \\ &= \frac{\left| -\frac{\kappa'}{\kappa^2} - \frac{1}{\kappa} \tau \frac{\sinh(\varphi + c)}{\cosh(\varphi + c)} \right|}{\cosh(\varphi + c)} \\ &= \frac{|\kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c) + \kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c)|}{\kappa^2 \cosh(\varphi + c)}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $T^* = \frac{\beta'}{\|\beta'\|_L}$, then we get

$$T^* = \cosh(\varphi + c) N - \sinh(\varphi + c) B. \quad (3.10)$$

Therefore, we have obtained Eq. (3.9). The curve β is not a unit speed curve. If we take the derivative of Eq. (3.10) with respect to s , we find

$$\begin{aligned}(T^*)' &= (\tau - \varphi') [B \cosh(\varphi + c) + N \sinh(\varphi + c)] - \kappa T \cosh(\varphi + c) \\ &= -\kappa T \cosh(\varphi + c)\end{aligned}$$

Since $T' = \left\| \alpha' \right\|_L \kappa N$, we have

$$(T^*)' = \left\| \beta' \right\|_L \kappa^* N^*.$$

Thus

$$\left\| \beta' \right\|_L \kappa^* N^* = -\kappa \cosh(\varphi + c) T.$$

Since the vectors N^* and T have the unit length, we get $N^* = -T$ or $N^* = T$. Since $B^* = N^* \wedge_L (-T^*)$, we have

$$B^* = -\sinh(\varphi + c)N + \cosh(\varphi + c)B. \quad (3.11)$$

Thus, the proof is completed. \square

Theorem 3.3 Let $\beta : I \rightarrow E_1^3$ be the evolute of the unit speed spacelike curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow E_1^3$. Let the Frenet vector fields, curvature and torsion of the curve β be T^*, N^*, B^*, κ^* and τ^* , respectively. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa^* &= \frac{\kappa^3 \cosh^3(\varphi + c)}{|\kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c) + \kappa' \cos(\varphi + c)|}, \quad \kappa > 0 \\ |\tau^*| &= \frac{\kappa^3 \cosh^2(\varphi + c) |\sinh(\varphi + c)|}{|\kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c) + \kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c)|}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof Since N^* and T have unit length, then taking norm from equality $\left\| \beta' \right\|_L \kappa^* N^* = -\kappa \cosh(\varphi + c) T$. We can write have

$$|\kappa^*| = \frac{\kappa \cosh(\varphi + c)}{\left\| \beta' \right\|_L} \quad (3.12)$$

$$= \kappa \cosh(\varphi + c) : \frac{|\kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c) + \kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c)|}{\kappa^2 \cosh(\varphi + c)},$$

$$|\kappa^*| = \frac{\kappa^3 \cosh^3(\varphi + c)}{\kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c) + \kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c)}$$

If we take the derivative Eq. (3.11) with respect to s , then we have

$$\begin{aligned}(B^*)' &= (\varphi' - \tau) [N \cosh(\varphi + c) - B \sinh(\varphi + c)] + \kappa T \sinh(\varphi + c) \\ &= \kappa T \sin(\varphi + c).\end{aligned}$$

Since $(B^*)' = \left\| \beta' \right\|_L \tau^* N^*$, we get

$$\left\| \beta' \right\|_L \tau^* N^* = \kappa T \sin(\varphi + c).$$

From the last equation, we must have

$$T^*(s) = N(s) \text{ or } T^*(s) = -N(s).$$

We assume that $T^*(s) = -N(s)$ then we find that

$$\begin{aligned} |\tau^*| &= \frac{\kappa |\sinh(\varphi + c)|}{\|\beta'\|} \\ &= \kappa |\sinh(\varphi + c)| : \frac{|\kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c) + \kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c)|}{\kappa^2 \cosh(\varphi + c)}, \\ |\tau^*| &= \frac{\kappa^3 \cosh^2(\varphi + c) |\sinh(\varphi + c)|}{|\kappa' \cosh(\varphi + c) + \kappa\tau \sinh(\varphi + c)|}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

□

Theorem 3.4 Let $\beta : I \longrightarrow E_1^3$ be the evolute of the unit speed spacelike curve $\alpha : I \longrightarrow E_1^3$. Let the curvature and torsion of the curve β be κ^* and τ^* , respectively. Then

$$\left| \frac{\tau^*}{\kappa^*} \right| = |\tanh(\varphi + c)|. \quad (3.14)$$

Furthermore, we denote by $\beta^{(1)}$ and $\beta^{(2)}$, the evolute curves obtained by using c_1 and c_2 instead of c , respectively. The tangents of the curves $\beta^{(1)}$ and $\beta^{(2)}$ at the points $\beta^{(1)}(s)$ and $\beta^{(2)}(s)$ intersect at the point $\alpha(s)$. The measure of the angle between the tangents is $c_1 - c_2$.

Proof The Eq. (3.14) is obtained easily by using Eq. (3.12) and Eq. (3.13), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\tau^*}{\kappa^*} \right| &= \frac{\kappa |\sinh(\varphi + c)|}{\|\beta'\|_L} : \frac{\kappa \cosh(\varphi + c)}{\|\beta'\|_L} \\ &= |\tanh(\varphi + c)|. \end{aligned}$$

The measure of the angle between the vectors $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(1)}(s)}$ and $\overrightarrow{V_2(s)}$, and between the vectors $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(2)}(s)}$ and $\overrightarrow{N(s)}$ are $\varphi(s) + c_1$ and $\varphi(s) + c_2$, respectively. The vector $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(1)}(s)}$ is parallel to the tangent of the curve $\beta^{(1)}$ at the point $\beta^{(1)}(s)$. The vector $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(2)}(s)}$ is parallel to the tangent of the curve $\beta^{(2)}$ at the point $\beta^{(2)}(s)$. Furthermore, since $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(1)}(s)}$, $\overrightarrow{\alpha(s)\beta^{(1)}(s)}$ and \overrightarrow{N} are perpendicular to the vector $\overrightarrow{T(s)}$, these three vectors are planar. Then, the measure of the angle between the tangents of the curves $\beta^{(1)}$ and $\beta^{(2)}$ at the points $\beta^{(1)}(s)$ and $\beta^{(2)}(s)$ is

$$\varphi(s) + c_1 - [\varphi(s) + c_2] = c_1 - c_2.$$

So, the proof is completed. □

Theorem 3.5 Suppose that, two different evolutes of the spacelike curve a spacelike principal normal curve α are given. Let the points on the evolutes of the curve α corresponding to the point P be P_1 and P_2 . Then the angle $\widehat{P_1 P P_2}$ is constant.

Proof Let the evolutes of the curve α be β and γ . Let the arc-length parameters of the α, β and γ be s, s^* and \widehat{s} , respectively. Let the curvatures of the curves α, β and γ be k, k^* and

\widehat{k} respectively. And let the Frenet vectors of the curves α , β and γ be $\{T, N, B\}, \{T^*, N^*, B^*\}$ and $\{\widehat{T}, \widehat{N}, \widehat{B}\}$. Then

$$T = N^*, T = \widehat{N}. \quad (3.15)$$

Since the curves β and γ are evolute, then

$$\langle T, T^* \rangle_L = \langle T, \widehat{T} \rangle_L = 0 \quad (3.16)$$

Therefore, if $f(s) = \langle T^*, \widehat{T} \rangle_L$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} (f)'(s) &= \langle (T^*)', \widehat{T} \rangle_L + \langle T^*, (\widehat{T})' \rangle_L \\ &= \left\langle \kappa^* N^* \frac{ds^*}{ds}, \widehat{T} \right\rangle_L + \left\langle T^*, \widehat{\kappa} \widehat{N} \frac{d\widehat{s}}{ds} \right\rangle_L \\ &= \kappa^* \frac{ds^*}{ds} \langle N^*, \widehat{T} \rangle_L + \widehat{\kappa} \frac{d\widehat{s}}{ds} \langle T^*, \widehat{N} \rangle_L \\ &= \kappa^* \frac{ds^*}{ds} \langle T, \widehat{T} \rangle_L + \widehat{\kappa} \frac{d\widehat{s}}{ds} \langle T^*, N^* \rangle_L \\ &= \kappa^* \frac{ds^*}{ds} \cdot 0 + \widehat{\kappa} \frac{d\widehat{s}}{ds} \cdot 0 \\ (f)'(s) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have $f(s) = \theta = \text{constant}$. Hence, $m(\widehat{P_1 P P_2}) = m(T^*, \widehat{T}) = \theta = \text{constant}$. \square

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